

POLLEN GERMINATION AND TUBE GROWTH IN FOUR SELECTED GENERA OF FAMILY MALVACEAE AND PAPAVERACEAE

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Abstract

Sexual reproduction in flowering plants comprises pollination, pollen tube growth and fertilization. Reproductive biology has been extensively used for successful cultivation and conservation of plant species. In the present study, pollen germination and pollen tube growth were carried out in some selected plants species of Agra, Uttar Pradesh for its reproductive success. All plants are useful in the making herbal medicines and belongs to families Malvaceae and Papaveraceae. Average pollen germination percentage were found 58% with 55.03 ± 5.01 μm long pollen tubes in *Hibiscus rosasinensis* followed by *Sida acuta* (55%), *Malva marutina* (50 %) and *Argemone maxicana* (47%) with 50.03 ± 4.01 , 55.03 ± 2.5 and 55.03 ± 2.02 μm long pollen tubes respectively. Pollen grains were observed 3 colpate, spheroidal spiny exine and 4-zonocolpate and reticulate. Pollen size and pollen tube length were measured by ocular micrometer under light microscope. The present work focused on pollen germination and pollen tube length in selected plants species for its reproductive success.

Keyword: *In-vitro* pollen germination, Malvaceae, Papaveraceae, Pollen tube.

Introduction

Sexual reproduction in flowering plants depends on delivery of the sperm to the egg, which occurs through a long polarized projection of a pollen cell, called the pollen tube (Alexander 2007). Pollen germination and growth of pollen tubes are important for morphological, physiological, biotechnological, ecological, evolutionary, biochemical and molecular biological studies (Ottavio *et al.*, 1992).

In vitro germination techniques have been extensively used on a variety of pollen systems. Such studies have provided considerable information on the physiology and biochemistry of pollen germination and pollen tube growth (Shivanna and Johri, 1985; Heslop-Harrison, 1987). Pollen germination and pollen tube growth are generally divided into four phases; imbibitions phase, lag phase, tube initiation phase and rapid tube elongation phase. (Linskens and Kroh, 1970). Pollen tube growth proceeds can be affected by many factors, including temperature, medium osmolarity and the availability of sucrose, calcium, zinc and boron (Taylor and Hepler, 1997).

Malva maruitiana, *Sida acuta* and *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* belongs to family Malvaceae growing at different places of Khandari Campus of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University Agra. These plants occurred in the tropical and sub tropical part of all over India and whole plant has a great medicinal importance which used in the making of herbal medicine. *Hibiscus* is commonly known as China rose or Gurhal. Flower is large, pedicellate, actinomorphic, trumpet shaped, polypetalous with red velvety long stigma. *S. acuta* as morning mallow or broom weed. Flower is pale yellow in color occurred throughout the year but depend on regional climate condition. *M. maruitiana* as common mallow. Flower is reddish purple and bright pinkish purple with dark stripes. *Argemone maxicana* is a herbs species belongs to family

Papaveraceae. It is commonly known as Prickly Poppy and Mexican prickly poppy and also known as a pili katheli or satyanashi. It is found in dry soils along roadsides, waste places, open fields and almost every part of India. Flowers occur at the end of branches and yellow in color.

The present work may help in providing considerable information on the physiology and biochemistry of pollen germination and pollen tube growth for its reproductive success.

Materials and Methods

The present work on Pollen germination and tube growth in four selected genera of family Malvaceae and Papaveraceae growing at different areas of Khandari Campus, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Agra were selected for the experiments of a M.Sc. short dissertation submitted in the partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Master of Science in Botany.

The pollen grains were collected from freshly dehisced anther and tested throughout the flowering period. The cavity slides are prepared by suspending the fresh pollen grains in a drop of Brewbaker and Kwack's medium (1963) by the using hanging drop culture method. This is the only convenient method by which the same pollen population can be observed over a period of time (Shivanna and Rangaswami, 1992). The culture medium sterilized by autoclaving. The rim of cavity was smeared with the petroleum jelly. A drop of the B.K. medium was placed on a cleaned dry cover slip. The drop was suspended in the centre of the cover slip and applied gentle pressure so that the cavity become sealed. The slides were kept in incubator under desired temperature condition. The temperature $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ is optimal for most pollen species. The pollen tube lengths were measured by

ocular micrometer under light microscope (Mckone and Webb, 1988).

Result and Discussion

The present investigation on Pollen germination and pollen tube length have clearly indicated that the Brewbaker and Kwack's medium was the best for in vitro pollen germination. The percentage of pollen germination and tube growth are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 : Pollen germination and tube length in target plants tested by Brewbaker and Kwack's medium.

Medium	<i>H. rosa sinensis</i>		<i>S. acuta</i>		<i>M. marutiana</i>		<i>A. mexicana</i>	
	PG.	TL ((μ m))	PG.	TL (μ m)	PG.	TL (μ m)	PG.	TL (μ m)
B.K. Medium	58%	55.03 \pm 5.01	55. %	50.03 \pm 4.01	50 %	55.03 \pm 2.5	47 %	55.03 \pm 2.02

Where, PG-Pollen germination, TL -Tube length

It is evident from data that the average range of pollen germination is 58% with 55.03 \pm 5.01 μ m long pollen tubes in *H. rosasinensis* when the maximum and minimum temperature range between 12 $^{\circ}$ C -24 $^{\circ}$ C with 60 % Related humidity. The average size of pollen grain was observed 80-160 μ m in diameter, globose to spheroidal. (Figure 1A, 2A and Table 1) Pollen germination is 55% with the 50.03 \pm 4.01 μ m long pollen tubes in *S. acuta* when temperature range between 12 $^{\circ}$ C -25 $^{\circ}$ C. The pollen grains were 3 colporate, spheroidal, spiny exine and average size of single pollen grain is 80 μ m in diameter, almost half the size of pollen of *H. rosasinensis*. (Figure 1B, 2B and Table 1). Pollen germination is 50 % with the 55.03 \pm 2.5 μ m long pollen tubes in *M. marutina*, when the temperature range between 12 $^{\circ}$ C -26 $^{\circ}$ C. Average size of pollen grain were observed 50-55 μ m in diameter and spheroidal, numerous. (Figure 1C, 2C and Table 1). In *A. maxicana* pollen germination were observed 47% with 55.03 \pm 2.02 μ m long pollen tubes when the temperature range between 18 $^{\circ}$ C -32 $^{\circ}$ C. The pollen grains were observed 3 zonicolpate, reticulate, monad and znicolpate with rounded ends (Figure 1D, 2D and Table 1).

Fig. 1. A: Plant of *H. rosasinensis*, **B:** *S. acuta*, **C:** *M. marutiana*, **D:** *A. mexicana*.

Fig. 2 : Pollen germination and pollen tube length of selected plants **A.** *H. rosasinensis*, **B.** *S. acuta*, **C.** *M. marutiana*, **D.** *A. mexicana*

The composition of a germination medium to obtain optimal responses has to empirically formulate for each species. Brewbaker and Kwack (1963) medium found to be suitable for most species. Different varieties need to different temperature germination. This is in accordance with the results reported in *Trichosanthes dioica* by Kumari *et al.* (2009) and in *Tribulus terrestris* by Ahmad *et al.* (2012). Pollen tube length was more or less found to be corresponding to the percentage of pollen germination. According to Kumar *et al.* (2010) in *Abutilon indicum* (L) sweet, *in vitro* pollen germination in Brewbaker and Kwack's medium is 56% with 55.03 \pm 6.01 μ m long pollen tubes. Singh *et al.* (2013) worked in *Sida cordifolia*, he reported that the pollen germination is 56.1% in same medium with 55.03 \pm 6.01 μ m long pollen tubes. Ahmad *et al.* (2012) working on *Tribulus terrestris* have also reported that with an increase in the concentration of sucrose in combination with 0.01% boric acid, germination percentage increased.

The present investigation also support the finding of Brewbaker and Kwack (1963) and demonstrates that for suitable pollen germination and tube growth, a medium containing sucrose, boric acid, calcium nitrate, magnesium sulphate and potassium nitrate is the best medium for germination and pollen tube growth.

Conclusion

In the present study, it was observed that the pollen germination and tube growth is closely related to the environment condition such as temperature and related humidity. Brewbaker and Kwack medium found to be suitable medium for germination and development of pollen tube. When boric acid was added to the medium, germination percentage as well as pollen tube growth increased. The present study may provide considerable information on the physiology and biochemistry of pollen germination and tube growth for its reproductive success.

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